

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT DURING MONOTONIC TENSILE TESTING IN CARBON REINFORCED POLYETHER ETHER KETONE

R. Van Daele, M. Wevers, I. Verpoest, P. De Meester
(Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Department of Metallurgy and
Materials Engineering, De Croylaan 2, B 3030 Heverlee, BELGIUM)

ABSTRACT

Damage in APC-2 is studied using in situ radiography, microscopy and moisture absorption techniques. It was found that in some of the laminates investigated, thin extended voids were present. These voids showed a fine, not necessarily interconnecting network. There are indications that matrix cracks initiate at these voids. APC-2 seems less sensitive to matrix failure under shear loading conditions than under normal loading conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The knowledge of the damage behaviour of fibre reinforced plastics under different loading conditions is necessary for the optimum application of these materials. This damage behaviour is influenced by several material properties, such as matrix properties, fibre properties, and fibre-matrix interface. In this study, emphasis will be put on the matrix properties of APC-2. The polymer used as matrix in APC-2, polyether ether ketone (PEEK), has some outstanding properties, such as its high strain to failure, its high fracture toughness and the relatively easy crystallisation. This paper will look closely into the behaviour of the matrix during monotonic tensile loading. The laminates were manufactured by I.C.I.Co, Wilton UK., using standard procedures and according to lay up requirements. No additional thermal treatment was performed.

INITIAL MATRIX DEFECTS IN APC-2

Since the thermal stresses in the 90° layers of $(0_2, 90_2)_s$ crossplies of APC-2 are rather high (50% of the failure stress of the $90^\circ UD^+$), there is the possibility that matrix cracks are present right after manufacturing and thus before mechanical testing.

In order to detect these initial matrix cracks the specimens were submerged in an X-ray opaque penetrant (di iodo methane, DIM). This penetrant fills the pores and matrix cracks, enabling the detection of these defects by X-ray radiography. The resulting radiographs show long thin lines, which were at first mistaken as matrix cracks. However, intensive study did not reveal any such matrix cracks at the edges. The hypothesis of interaction of the penetrant with APC-2 (stress crazing) was also investigated and finally dropped when prolonged stress corrosion tests didn't reveal any damage due to the interaction of the liquid penetrant. Then, the possibility that these thin lines were voids, was investigated.

Several virgin crossply APC-2 laminates were submerged for one day in the penetrant, and the edges were subsequently polished and studied using optical microscopy. This revealed small voids (about $5\mu m$ in diameter) in the laminate, predominantly at the

interface of the different plies. These voids were photographed and compared with the voids present in the material after an additional polishing step (which removed about 20 μ m). The re-occurrence of the voids at the same location times and times again, proved the existence of thin long pores in the material of at least 100 μ m deep.

Fig 1 : X-ray radiograph of APC-2 crossply, as received. The specimen was submerged for 1 hour in DIM.

Fig 2 : voids present in APC-2, as received. Magnification 300x.

The existence of these pores was carefully scrutinized, since the existence of such voids is considered important in damage initiation at the sites of these voids. Since many of the pores had a linkage with the edges of the specimens, it was attempted to fill the cracks with a fluid and calculate the void content (of the voids with a connection to the edges or to other voids).

Fig. 3 : Evolution of the weight during the moisture absorption and desorption experiments, both for APC-2 and PEEK 450G, penetrated in DIM.

Hereto, samples of the same geometry were taken of APC-2 crossplies and of pure PEEK 450G resin. The samples were dried during 12 days. One sample was submerged for 24 hours in DIM and another for 48 hours in ethanol. The specimens were hereafter dried with an absorbent tissue and weighed for the first time after 10 minutes. This time was used to enable the penetrant at the outer surface of the specimen to evaporate.

The samples were then redried in an oven at 120°C. The weight loss during drying, weight gain after penetration and weight loss during the subsequent drying is represented in figure 3 and 4.

Fig. 4 : Evolution of the weight during the moisture absorption and desorption experiments, for APC-2, penetrated in ethanol.

These results show that, taking into account the density of the penetrant, there is no difference in the penetration properties of ethanol and di iodo methane. The thermoplastic matrix PEEK itself doesn't absorb much penetrant : about 0.03 vol%. The weight gain after absorption completely disappears after 1 day of drying and the penetrant is most probable only present in small surface cracks. APC-2 however, absorbs ethanol and diiodomethane more readily than the pure matrix. Using the density of ethanol and diiodomethane, the void content of the samples were established at 0.6 vol% with DIM and 0.5 vol% in ethanol. This absorbed moisture remains for the larger part in the crossply laminate even during prolonged drying. Radiographs show that the penetrant has disappeared at the edges of the specimen, but is still present in the interior of the specimens.

IN SERVICE MATRIX CRACKING

The initiation and propagation of matrix cracks is influenced by a number of parameters. First, we have the material properties itself like G_{1C} and failure strain (ϵ_f), plastic deformability of the matrix and the properties of fibre-matrix interface. Secondly, the processing parameters change the laminate resistance to matrix cracking by altering the residual stresses, crystallinity (thermoplastics), presence of voids, and degree of cure(thermosets). Thirdly, the fibre volume fraction, the local geometry and laminate lay-up will produce stress and strain concentrations which will largely influence matrix cracking.

APC-2 is reported to have an excellent interface², and PEEK has a very high strain to failure and matrix toughness, even when crystallized. One could expect to have good resistance to matrix cracking in APC-2. The thermal stresses involved on $(0_2 90_2)_s$ laminates however, are rather high (40MPa or 50% of ϵ_f of 90° UD laminate) and will decrease the resistance to matrix cracking.

In order to study the matrix crack growth, the above mentioned pores and voids first have to be filled with a penetrant with lower X-ray absorption than the one used for matrix crack detection³. Using adequate X-ray conditions, the pores present in the laminate can be disregarded.

The study of matrix cracks in APC-2 was performed on two different laminate types : $(0_x 90_y)_s$ and $(\pm\theta)_{2s}$ in order to create different loading conditions on the matrix : normal and shear loading.

The tensile specimens used were 250mm long, 20mm wide and were provided with 60 mm long aluminium end tabs.

The tests were performed incrementally, i.e. a certain strain was applied while the specimen was surrounded by a penetrant, then the specimen was left submerged in the penetrant for 10 additional minutes to let the penetrant penetrate the cracks completely. Then the penetrant was removed and the sides of the specimen were cleared of excess penetrant, to be followed by a contact radiography.

Normal loading of matrix : $(0_2 90_2)_s$ and $(0 90_3)_s$ laminates

A series of radiographs was taken every 0.1 % strain. The number of cracks and the crack length was determined for each strain increment. The crack length per area (measured on a 24x20mm area) is given as a function of applied strain in figure 5. The first cracks start to develop rather early when compared to typical carbon epoxy laminates.

Fig 5 : matrix crack length evolution during a incremental monotonic tensile test on $(0_2 90_2)_s$ APC-2.

However, once a crack is formed (at the edges of the specimen), it grows only slowly into the laminate and it does not necessarily grow through the whole width of the 90° plies. It is assumed that the matrix cracks start to form at the voids, since the matrix cracks detected with the X-ray radiographs have the very same location as the voids present in the material. A confirmation of still has to be looked for using optical microscopy. The fracture surfaces were investigated for debonding and matrix deformation using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). No indication of debonding was found.

Shear loading of matrix : $(\pm 12)_2s$ and $(\pm 45)_2s$

The $(\pm 45)_2s$ laminates, as the $(0_2 90_2)_s$ laminates, clearly showed voids. However, no matrix cracks were initiated, even at high deformation (up to 26% deformation could be reached). The laminate deformed plastically, leaving a specimen with a rough surface.

The $(\pm 12)_2s$ laminates did not show any voids. One of the possibilities is that this laminate was produced under different conditions, but this could not be verified since production was not done at our own facilities. A good resin flow would certainly improve the evacuation of entrapped air. During deformation, no matrix cracks formed until at 95% of the failure strain, when very small matrix cracks initiated at the edges and along the fibre orientation.

SEM showed also in these laminates a good adhesion of the matrix to the fibre.

Nowhere on the fracture surfaces, bare or partly bare fibres were observed.

CONCLUSION

Voids exist in APC-2 laminates and are probably the cause of matrix crack initiation in crossply laminates. Production of void free laminates is therefore of utmost importance. Under normal stress conditions matrix cracks do form at an early stage, not withstanding the superior matrix properties. The matrix seems less sensitive to matrix cracking under shear conditions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The preceding text presents research results of the Belgian programme on interuniversity attraction poles initiated by the Belgian state -Prime Minister's Office -Science Policy Programming. The scientific responsibility is assumed by its authors. The authors also wish to thank ICI for the production of the laminates.

REFERENCES

- 1 Jeronimidis, G. Parkyn, A.T., Journal of Composite Materials, 22, may 1988, p401-415.
- 2 Peacock, J.A. et al. Composite Interfaces, ed. Ishida and Koenig, Proc. of First Int. Conf. on Composite Interfaces, Cleveland Ohio, 1986, p 143-149.
- 3 Van Daele, R., Verpoest, I., Wevers, M., De Meester, P., ECCM3, Bordeaux, March 1989, to be published.

6. Fatigue and Fracture

Handwritten text, possibly a title or header, appearing as a faint, mirrored bleed-through from the reverse side of the page.